

Next Steps

We are now in the most exciting phase of the project, where qualitative data collected during stage 1 has been carefully analyzed from socio-cultural, legal and gender perspectives, thanks to the effort of all consortium partners. These individual documents, concentrating on different aspects of our research, were submitted in August to the Project Coordinator, Francisco Güell, from the Institute for Culture and Society. In September, they will elaborate a draft document with a synthesis of all the analyses done to be the bases of the recommendation guidelines. Finally, that draft will be discussed and optimized among the Consortium Partners during an in-person meeting organized in Pamplona, Spain, at the beginning of October 2022.

The resulting document will be then validated in one final workshop in Brussels, a meeting that will see consortium members meet a sample of target citizens from the eight countries taken into consideration for this research. Finally, the idea is to share the eight national guidelines with a group of citizens of each country to get their feedback.

This final validation will result in 8 documents for each sample country containing recommendations from a gender, socio-cultural and legal point of view. Based on this document, B2-InF will elaborate different recommendation guidelines for the various stakeholders (as Policy briefs or guidelines for the industry) for each country and will also write an international guideline for the European Commission institutions, which will include a scientific strategy meant to be disseminated in Congress, highlighting the most exciting findings of the analysis.

In 2023, during the last stage of B2-inF, the consortium will focus on elaborating guidelines and disseminating the final results among the scientific community, policymakers, industry stakeholders and citizens.